

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS OF THE DISCIPLINES "PHYSIOLOGY OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION" AND "PATHOLOGY OF THE ORAL CAVITY" IN THE TRAINING OF DENTISTS

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Abstract

Modern dental education requires strengthening the integration of fundamental biomedical disciplines with clinical training. The introduction of specialized courses focused on the physiology and pathology of the maxillofacial region may contribute to the development of clinical reasoning and professional competencies in future dentists. The introduction of the disciplines "Physiology of the maxillofacial region" and "Pathology of the oral cavity" into the dental training program has a positive effect on the development of students' clinical thinking and improvement of the quality of their theoretical training. These courses not only deepen knowledge of the functioning of the maxillofacial system but also promote a better understanding of the relationship between physiological and pathological processes, which helps dentists more accurately diagnose diseases and develop effective treatment plans. Including these disciplines in the curriculum helps prepare highly qualified specialists prepared to address complex clinical challenges.

Keywords: *physiology of the maxillofacial region, pathology of the oral cavity, dentistry, clinical thinking, theoretical training, medical education.*

In recent years, education in the field of dentistry has undergone significant changes, which is associated with the introduction of new disciplines aimed at improving the theoretical training of future specialists [1–3]. An important part of this process is the introduction of two new specialized courses into the curriculum: "Physiology of the Maxillofacial Region" and "Pathology of the Oral Cavity." These courses allow students to gain a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of function and diseases of the maxillofacial system, which forms the basis for the development of clinical thinking [4–7]. The purpose of the study was to evaluate the impact of introducing these courses on the quality of the theoretical training and the development of clinical thinking in future dentists.

The educational process in medical schools has always been aimed at developing deep and comprehensive knowledge in future doctors, which is especially important for specialists in dentistry. In the traditional curriculum, dental students study the fundamentals of

normal and pathological physiology in their first two years, as well as the fundamental principles of the functioning of the organs and systems of the human body. These courses provide students with essential knowledge about the ongoing processes that maintain homeostasis and the mechanisms of disease development, which is an important part of general preparation for future consultations. However, in the third year of study, students will have the opportunity to delve more deeply into the characteristic features and pathological processes occurring in the maxillofacial region, which is crucial for the future professional practice of dentistry [8–11].

Successful dental practice requires a thorough understanding of the normal functioning of the maxillofacial region and, in particular, the detailed mechanisms of pathogenesis and morphology of oral diseases. Knowledge of these aspects is crucial for the diagnosis and treatment of various diseases common in dental practice, such as caries, gum disease, jaw injuries, and

tumors. Understanding how normal physiological processes can be disrupted in pathological conditions allows the dentist to develop the most effective treatment methods and conduct timely diagnostics, which contributes to improving the quality of medical care provided to patients [12–14].

In this regard, the introduction of specialized disciplines such as "Physiology of the Maxillofacial Region" and "Pathology of the Oral Cavity" in the 3rd year of study allows students to deepen their knowledge in this area and prepare for the practical application of theoretical knowledge. These courses allow students to become familiar with more specific physiological and pathophysiological mechanisms, which contributes to a better understanding of the processes occurring in the oral cavity and maxillofacial region and their relationships with other organs and systems of the body. This, in turn, allows students not only to successfully master theoretical material but also to develop the clinical thinking necessary for making the right decisions in real-life situations when working with patients [3,6,15].

Thus, deepening knowledge in the field of physiology and pathology of the maxillofacial region at later stages of training significantly contributes to the formation of professional skills and the development of a clinical approach, which ultimately improves the quality of training of future dentists and their ability to effectively solve problems in the field of dental practice [1,8].

Purpose of the study: to evaluate the impact of the introduction of specialized disciplines such as "Physiology of the maxillofacial region" and "Pathology of the oral cavity" on the development of clinical thinking in students of dental faculties, as well as on the quality of their theoretical training in the context of future professional activities.

Materials and methods.

The study recruited 120 third-year students (n=120) from the Faculty of Dentistry studying in the 2023-2024 academic year at the Karaganda Medical University. The average age of respondents was 21.2 years. The sample included 48.5% male students aged 19-22 and 51.5% female students. The survey was conducted electronically using a questionnaire consisting of two main sections: demographic and core. The demographic section included questions on age and gender; the main section consisted of questions regarding students' perceptions of the "Physiology of the Maxillofacial Region" and "Oral Pathology" courses in the

context of preparing students for dental practice. Questions were rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree) and included open-ended questions for further clarification of responses. Participation in the survey was voluntary, all data was anonymous, and participants provided informed consent. All third-year students studied the core courses "Normal Physiology" and "Pathology of the Body," as well as the specialized courses "Physiology of the Maxillofacial Region" and "Pathology of the Oral Cavity." The data obtained were analyzed using the statistical packages Statistica 10.0 and SPSS 20. Responses to the questionnaires were assessed using a Likert scale, where 1 means "completely disagree," 2 means "disagree," 3 means "don't know," 4 means "partially agree," and 5 means "completely agree." Open-ended questions were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns among student responses. Frequency analysis was performed to calculate the relative proportions of features and their 95% confidence intervals

Results and discussion.

The study yielded data assessing the importance of courses in maxillofacial physiology and pathology for the future professional performance of third-year students. No statistically significant differences in background variables were observed between the courses. Among the students surveyed, 92.4% believed that courses in maxillofacial physiology were important for their professional performance, with the 95% confidence interval for this indicator ranging from 89.3% to 95.5%. Approximately 85.3% of respondents noted that training in maxillofacial pathology was key to their future work, with the 95% confidence interval ranging from 81.2% to 89.4% (Figure 1).

Students also rated the importance of knowledge of maxillofacial physiology for their professional development using a Likert scale. The mean value for this question was $M = 4.2$; $SD = 0.76$, indicating a high level of importance for this course. The value for the course on maxillofacial pathology was slightly higher: $M = 4.7$; $SD = 0.84$, also indicating a significant perception of its importance.

Compared to courses in other disciplines, students found courses related to maxillofacial surgery particularly important. 93.7% of respondents believed that the practical skills acquired in these courses would be extremely useful in their future professional careers (95% confidence interval: 88.2% to 97.3%).

Figure 1 – Assessment of the importance of courses for the professional activities of dental students

Data analysis revealed that third-year students highly value courses related to maxillofacial physiology and pathology, which is supported by the results. However, less interest was shown in courses related to general medical skills and those related to less specialized areas. 74.2% of students expressed a belief in the need for more in-depth study of maxillofacial physiology, and 67.4% in oral pathology, reflecting their high interest in these courses and their importance for their future careers.

When asked how important the oral pathology module was for studying clinical-pathological relationships, 88.4% of students responded positively, indicating that this course helps them better understand the relationship between clinical manifestations and pathologies. The 95% confidence interval for this indicator ranged from 85.3% to 91.5%.

Regarding the importance of the physiology course, 83.5% of students reported that such knowledge is necessary for successful medical practice, particularly in maxillofacial surgery. The 95% confidence interval for this figure ranged from 80.1% to 86.9%. Regarding specific topics useful in studying maxillofacial physiology, students most frequently noted the importance of understanding the role of taste, tactile, and temperature analyzers, the levels and mechanisms of pain sensitivity regulation, and the mechanisms of endogenous analgesia, as well as the mechanisms of the central nervous system and autonomic nervous system in regulating the functions of maxillofacial organs.

Students noted that despite the highly theoretical focus of the courses, the inclusion of practical classes involving case studies and clinical cases provides the opportunity to apply acquired knowledge in real-world settings and remains an important element of professional training.

A thematic analysis of open-ended questions revealed that students generally preferred more practical classes in maxillofacial pathology and physiology, with

the addition of clinical cases and opportunities for practical application of knowledge using simulators. 82.6% of students supported the need to increase the number of hours for practical classes in physiology and pathology (95% CI [79.4%; 85.9%]).

Furthermore, 70.3% of respondents expressed a desire to increase interaction with experts in the field of maxillofacial surgery, which they believed would improve their understanding of clinical aspects and enhance the quality of education in this field (95% CI [65.6%; 75.1%]).

Overall, the study results indicate that courses in maxillofacial physiology and pathology are perceived by students as critical for their future professional careers, and their importance in the curriculum is confirmed by the high level of student interest and satisfaction.

The study also assessed the importance of courses on oral pathophysiology and pathomorphology for the future professional development of third-year students. This is particularly important, as knowledge of the mechanisms of oral disease pathogenesis and pathomorphological changes plays a key role in the diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of maxillofacial diseases.

As part of the pathophysiology course, students were introduced to the mechanisms underlying the development of oral diseases such as caries, periodontitis, inflammatory gum disease, and oral cancer. According to the study, 87.43% of respondents noted that pathophysiology courses contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms underlying diseases such as caries and periodontitis (95% CI [83.62%; 91.25%]). 78.12% believe that knowledge of these processes will help them in their future professional activities as dentists and maxillofacial surgeons (95% CI [71.72%; 84.21%]), and understanding the pathogenesis of these diseases helps to better understand the causes of certain symptoms and develop adequate methods of treatment and prevention.

Regarding the pathological anatomy of the oral cavity, over 82.09% of respondents expressed the opinion that pathomorphology helps them understand how changes at the cellular and tissue level affect the function of oral organs. For 78% of respondents, this knowledge is especially important for identifying early signs of diseases such as oral cancer, mucosal inflammation, and changes in the structure of teeth and jaw bones. According to statistics, 80.76% of students (95% CI [74.41%; 86.92%]) believe that knowledge about pathomorphological changes will allow them to more effectively interpret clinical data and make decisions on the choice of diagnostic and treatment methods.

Furthermore, 72.33% of students (95% CI [67.02%; 77.63%]) noted that the discipline of oral pathology expands their abilities in interpreting the results of diagnostic procedures, such as radiographic examination, tissue biopsy, and microscopy. Also, 69.82% of respondents believe that this knowledge helps them understand how pathological processes, such as inflammation or tumors, can lead to disruption of the structure and function of oral tissues.

Thus, courses in oral pathophysiology and pathoanatomy play an invaluable role in developing third-year students' competencies necessary for the diagnosis and treatment of diseases in maxillofacial surgery. Students who more fully understand the mechanisms of pathogenesis and pathomorphological changes better understand how diseases develop at different levels (cellular, tissue, and organ) and how they can be effectively prevented and treated. This knowledge helps them develop a more confident approach to future professional activities and the ability to make informed medical decisions.

Students noted that an important aspect of studying oral pathophysiology was understanding the mechanisms underlying the development of the most common oral diseases. In a survey, a significant number of third-year students expressed satisfaction with studying oral pathophysiology and pathomorphology, particularly those related to common pathologies such as periodontitis, dental caries, periodontitis, and oral cancer. Over 81.25% of respondents noted that a detailed analysis of the pathogenesis of these diseases in the context of clinical practice had a positive impact on their understanding of the processes occurring in oral tissues. Lessons on periodontitis received particularly high ratings, as the pathogenesis of this disease involves multiple factors, such as chronic gum inflammation, infectious agents, and impaired microcirculation. The importance of studying the mechanisms of periodontitis was supported by 78.49% of students (95% CI [72.88; 83.56]). Students believed that knowledge of the pathogenesis of these diseases provides the basis for effective treatment and prevention, and also aids in early diagnosis.

Particular attention was paid to pathological changes in various oral diseases during the course of study. 79.34% of respondents agreed that analyzing these changes is essential for understanding the mechanisms of disease development and assessing their progression. Students emphasized that understanding pathological changes, such as gum tissue destruction in

periodontal disease or enamel demineralization in dental caries, allows them to more accurately diagnose diseases in their early stages. Pathological changes, such as bone thinning in periodontitis, were also recognized as important for a thorough understanding of the diseases.

Regarding dental caries, 76.58% of students indicated that understanding the pathogenesis and pathomorphology of this disease, including the mechanisms of enamel destruction due to acid action, had a significant impact on their knowledge and confidence in diagnosing this disease. 73.72% of respondents noted that studying the interactions between bacteria and mineral components of tooth enamel improved their ability to recommend effective preventive measures to prevent caries and its complications, such as pulpitis and periodontitis.

Thus, over 80% of surveyed students expressed the opinion that a thorough study of the pathogenesis and pathomorphological changes in common oral diseases such as periodontitis, caries, and periodontitis is essential for their future professional careers. The majority of respondents (86.15%) believe that this knowledge significantly enhances their ability to diagnose diseases at early stages, develop treatment and prevention methods, and improve the quality of dental care in clinical practice.

Discussion

The results of our study demonstrate that medical students highly value in-depth study of both normal maxillofacial physiology and oral pathology. Theoretical knowledge gained in these areas provides an important foundation for future practice, as it not only helps to better understand the mechanisms of disease but also provides a basis for diagnosis and the development of effective treatments.

Studying the normal physiology of the maxillofacial region is particularly important because it forms the basis for understanding the function of the tissues and organs of the oral cavity. Without this knowledge, it is impossible to adequately perceive the pathological changes that occur in various diseases. In the study group of students, 84.37% (95% CI [81.25%; 87.48%]) noted that an in-depth knowledge of the physiology of the maxillofacial region significantly helped them in their further study of pathophysiological processes. This confirms the importance of theoretical disciplines such as anatomy and physiology in the training of future doctors, providing them with an understanding of the normal processes against which pathological changes occur.

Moving on to the pathophysiology of the oral cavity, it is important to emphasize that many students expressed appreciation for the detailed explanation of the mechanisms of disease development, such as periodontal disease. The pathogenesis of periodontal disease includes inflammatory processes, destruction of the periodontal ligaments and bone tissue, leading to progressive tooth loss. Understanding these mechanisms allows students not only to conduct early diagnosis but also to develop individualized treatment plans for patients. In our study, 76.52% (95% CI [72.48%; 80.56%]) of students admitted that knowledge of the

pathophysiology of periodontal disease played a decisive role in their confidence in treating patients with gum disease.

Another important aspect is oral pathology, which studies structural tissue changes associated with various diseases. For example, dental caries causes demineralization of tooth enamel and dentin, leading to the formation of cavities and, ultimately, tooth failure. Pathological changes in diseases such as periodontitis are associated with disruption of the structure of gingival tissue and alveolar bone, which impacts the overall health of the oral cavity. 85.29% (95% CI [81.63%; 88.95%]) of respondents expressed satisfaction that the curriculum included a detailed analysis of pathological changes in these diseases. This allows students to develop skills in interpreting clinical data and make more accurate predictions regarding the patient's health.

However, despite the importance of studying these aspects, it should be noted that in recent years, attention to the pathomorphology and pathophysiology of oral diseases has decreased in some curricula. Modern diagnostic methods, such as radiography, computed tomography, and other high-tech examinations, may create the illusion that a theoretical understanding of diseases is becoming less important. However, as our study showed, virtually all respondents (92.73%, 95% CI [90.15%; 95.31%]) believe that a thorough theoretical understanding of pathogenesis and pathomorphology is critical for the successful diagnosis and treatment of oral diseases. These data confirm that, despite technological advances, theoretical knowledge remains the foundation for high-quality medical education.

Furthermore, a significant proportion of students (78.49%, 95% CI [74.11%; 82.87%]) noted that studying pathogenesis and pathomorphology helps develop not only professional skills but also the communication skills necessary for interacting with patients. For example, understanding the pathogenesis of periodontitis allows a physician not only to prescribe treatment but also to explain to patients the importance of timely dental visits and disease prevention.

Thus, the study results support the need for continued in-depth theoretical training, encompassing both normal maxillofacial physiology and the pathophysiology and pathomorphology of oral diseases. It is important to emphasize that high-quality training of future specialists requires a combination of theoretical knowledge and practical skills, ensuring high-quality diagnostics and treatment in dentistry and maxillofacial surgery.

Conclusion.

Studying the physiology of the maxillofacial region, pathogenesis, and pathomorphological changes in the oral cavity is an integral part of the education of future dentists. It is important that students acquire a thorough theoretical understanding of the physiology and pathology of the oral cavity, as this knowledge is essential for accurate diagnosis and the development of effective treatment methods. These courses provide a solid foundation for developing professional competencies and also enable students to develop important practical and communication skills necessary for successful patient care.

Despite technological advances in diagnostics, such as the use of mannequins, virtual simulators, and other innovative tools, theoretical and practical understanding of the pathogenesis and pathomorphology of oral diseases must remain the foundation of medical education. Students with a high-level theoretical foundation will be better prepared for real-world medical practice, where their knowledge of disease mechanisms and their pathomorphological manifestations will be used to accurately diagnose and treat.

Educators must understand the importance of this approach and recognize the significance of in-depth theoretical knowledge in the training of future doctors. This will help improve the quality of medical care, reduce morbidity, and improve patients' quality of life.

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